

The famous commentator on Manusmriti was of the opinion that they should be honoured, treated with kindness and should be recognised of gifts.

The legal implication of the rule that they be treated with kindness is that these persons should be given special privileges. They were under the state's patronage and protection because they were incapable to direct their own affairs. These persons were given special privileges in the matters of legal, social and penal affairs. The Kārttikeya have vividly mentioned that transactions of foreign people had to be decided by the judges themselves. These persons not only enjoyed special privileges in matters of law but the judges were their official legal advisers who had to transact without any fee.

The state also dealt with the state's old and poor. It was a kind of a government relief and assistance scheme to infirm, old, diseased persons, distressed and helpless persons with maintenance (dāna) allowances. It is not clear whether this assistance scheme was completely free or the state asked these persons to do something for the state. However, it is mentioned that the persons not related (anandhāna) were necessarily supported. They had to study science, grammar, etc. in order to become government spies. Kārttikeya while introducing a very progressive scheme of government relief and assistance had also in mind the maintenance needs of the state.

1. Medh. on Mn. VIII, 395.
2. Mn. VII, 163.
3. See also A.S. Alker, The Position of Women in Hindu Civil Law.
4. Anthology, 20, 1-2.
5. J. Steinbach, Judicial Studies in Ancient India, p. 225.
6. Dharmaśāstra-vyākhyāna, p. 240.
7. Anthology, 47, 18.
8. Anthology, 20, 2-4.

Gandhi, Gandhi etc. in the old Hindu temples on the fort prove its prolonged occupation through centuries.

The name 'Raisen' appears to be a corrupt form of 'Rajiv'.

THE HILL-FORT OF RAISEN

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The fort of Raisen, rising high above the plains in the vicinity of Sanchi and Bhopal, was once considered as the gateway to Southern India. Its history covers nearly 700 years from 12th cent. AD onwards. At first it appears to have served the Hindu rulers, but subsequently it went on changing hands. Iltutmish Alauddin Khilji, Sultans of Malwa and Gujarat, Rana Sanga, Lodis of Delhi, Humayun, Sher-shah, Akbar, Durgawati, Aurangzeb, Shah Alam II, Nawabs of Bhopal etc. all held sway over the fort. In 1901 it was declared as a historical monument of national importance by the Central Government. The paper gives a graphic and romantic picture of the vicissitudes that the fort passed through the centuries and describes its architecture briefly.

The Raisen town and its fort are situated at 23° 20' North and 77° 47' East, 20 kilometers south of Vidisa and 45 kilometers east of Bhopal. The fort stands on an outlier of a comparatively high-oblong sandstone rock about 594 meters above the sea-level¹ and about 150 metres above the town of Raisen. It is approachable from Vidisa via Sanchi and Bhopal by road. The nearest railway stations connecting the buses to Raisen are Salamatpur and Sanchi between the Vidisa and the Bhopal railway stations.

During 1931-32 a votive *stupa* bearing an inscription in the 2nd cent. A.D. script was found in the fort. Images of Kārttikeya,

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1. *Bhopal State Gazetteer* (Vol. III), compiled by C.E. Luard, Calcutta, 1908, pp. 111-112.

Gaṇeśa, Nandī etc. in the old Hindu temples on the fort prove its prolonged occupation through centuries.¹

The name "Raisen" appears to be a corrupt form of 'Rājavāsinī' or of Rai Singh,² the name of the fort's founder. Most probably, it was raised by some Hindu king, preferably Rai Singh long ago; but his account is no more available. It grew to its present form in course of atleast 700 years.

In 1234-35, Raisen is said to have fallen alongwith Vidisa to the Delhi slave Sultan Iltutmish.³ In 1292-93 it was captured by another Delhi Sultan Alāuddīn Khiljī.⁴ An inscription of 890 A.H. = 1474 A.D. on the college-mosque of Ghanīmūl-Mulk inside the fort (*i.e.* present Bārādārī) shows its Muslim occupation.⁵ A Persian inscription in the same mosque, above its central mehrab, states that Malik Rādī, son of Chhajjū or Ghanīmūl Mulk, constructed the mosque, its dome and bāgh-i-kbur⁶ in 1489-90. Later on, this mosque came to be known as the mosque of Pamīka (Pālmykā⁷). It appears as if it was erected on the ruins of an earlier Hindu temple. In 1491 the fort was in possession of Ghiyāsuddīn Khiljī of Malwa.⁸ During the reign of Nāsiruddīn Khiljī of Malwa (1500) his eldest son Shihābuddīn was the governor of Raisen, Dhāmonī and Vidisa districts.⁹ Mahmūd II of Malwa (1510) also held it for

1. *Annual Report*, Archaeological Survey of India, 1935-36, p. 48.
2. *Bhopal State Gazetteer* (Vol. III), p. 112.
3. *The Cambridge History of India* (Vol. III), 1958, Delhi, p. 55; *Bhopal State Gazetteer* (Vol. III), p. 76.
4. *The Cambridge History of India* (Vol. III), p. 55; *Bhopal State Gazetteer* (Vol. III), p. 76.
5. *History of Bhopal*, translated by H.C. Barstow, Calcutta, 1876, pp. 209-10.
6. *Ep. Ind.* (MO.) (1933-34), pp. 24-26, Pl. XIb. (Inscription No. 246).
7. *Annual Report* (ASI) 1935-36, p. 27 and *Annual Report* (ASI) 1930-34, p. 49.
8. *Ibid.*, 1935-36, p. 100.
9. *The Cambridge History of India* (Vol. III), p. 245.

a time.¹ After 1517 Rāṇā Sāngā defeated Ibrāhīm Lodī and annexed Raisen, Kālpī and Chanderī to his kingdom of Mewār.² This shows that Raisen was in possession of the Lodī kings of Delhi as well. In 1520 Silhādī came to own the fort.³ In 1531 he annexed Malwa; and Bahādur Shāh of Gujarat, who had conquered Malwa from Mahmūd II, made over the city of Ujjain, Parganās of Bhilsā, including the Raisen fort and Ashṭā in Jāgīr to Silhādī. Silhādī was a Gahlot, Tonwāra (Tomar) or a Purbiā Rajput.⁴ In a Raisen fort inscription of 5th February, 1526 he is referred to as Sālāhadadu.⁵ There is a "Purbīyā Muhallā" in the present town of Raisen. About 100 years ago, it was chiefly habited by the Kānyakubja Brāhmaṇas who were noted wrestlers and fighters. Silhādī had married Durgāwatī, a princess-daughter of Rāṇā Sāngā of Chittor.⁶ The southern wall of the temple-mosque (Sher Shāh-mosque) inside the fort contains an inscribed stone-slab recording the name of Sangrām Shāh. Silhādī's brother was Medinī Rāi, the Rajput-minister of Mahmūd II of Malwa.⁷ The Rāos of Raisen paid tribute to the Rāṇā.⁸ Silhādī, the Tomar chief of Raisen, mediated between Rāṇā Sāngā and Bābar for the battle of Khānuā near Sikri in 1527.⁹ It is said that he maintained four bands of dancing girls, whose clothes were all of gold brocade and many of them were Muslim girls from Sind.¹⁰ He is also said to have captured the widow of the Sultan Nāsiruddīn of Delhi.¹¹ Later, when Silhādī made himself strongly established at

1. *The First Afghan Empire in India* (1451-1526 A.D.) by A.B. Pandey, Calcutta, 1956, p. 146.
2. *The Delhi Sultanate* (The History and Culture of the Indian People) by R.C. Majumdar and A.D. Pusalkar, Bombay, 1960, pp. 343-44.
3. *Bhopal State Gazetteer* (Vol. III), p. 112.
4. *Ibid.*, p. 76.
5. *Annual Report* (ASI) 1935-36, p. 100.
6. *Bhopal State Gazetteer* (Vol. III), p. 77.
7. *The Cambridge History of India* (Vol. III), p. 327.
8. *Ibid.*, p. 529.
9. *Ibid.*, p. 530.
10. *Bhopal State Gazetteer* (Vol. III), pp. 112-13.
11. *The Delhi Sultanate*, p. 186.

Raisen, Bahādur Shāh of Gujarat was somewhat alarmed and on the usual pretext, that Silhādī was maintaining Muslim women in his harem, he planned to crush him as soon as the occasion arose.¹ Once, Bahādur Shāh came down to Mandu and sent for Silhādī to return to Mandu from Raisen but without avail. Bahādur then deputed Nassan Khān to bring Silhādī to the Mandu court. This was duly accomplished and Nassan Khān warned Bahādur Shāh that if released, Silhādī would certainly join hands with the Rāṇā. Silhādī was accordingly arrested at Dhar and his troops were dispersed.²

Now Lakhman Singh, a brother of Silhādī held the Raisen fort in absence of the latter. In order to capture the fort Bahādur Shāh sent Imādul-Mulk-Malikjī to engage Lakhman Singh in battle in January, 1532. The Rajputs attacked the Muslim forces but were repulsed back to the fort, because Bahādur's artillery under Mustafā Rūmī Khān managed to destroy two of the bastions and several yards of the fort-wall. In the meantime Silhādī had to accept Islam and was renamed as "Salāhuddīn". He was conditionally permitted to meet Lakhman Singh and both of them waited for a relieving reinforcement from the Rāṇā of Chittor. Silhādī's youngest son with a force of 2000 men was also sent towards Chittor to hasten the military help. But Muslim forces intercepted and slew Silhādī's son. Silhādī was then sent again to Mandu. Bahādur sent another force to check the advancing army of the Rāṇā accompanying Silhādī's another son Bhopat.³ In a Raisen fort inscription of the 5th Feb. 1526 Bhopat is referred to as Bhūmapati Shāh. The Muslim forces engaged 2000 Rajputs under Pūran Mal, another son of Silhādī. By that time, Bahādur himself reached Raisen. Lakhman Singh agreed to surrender to Bahādur on the condition that Silhādī was pardoned. Accordingly, Silhādī was freed; but he had to follow another programme of events. Lakhman Singh and others persuaded him to perform Jauhar and then fight to the last. Rānī Durgāwati cautioned Silhādī with noble words—"We have lived all our lives here as chiefs; there is nothing left to you than to kill the women, burn them and then die yourself fighting." Silhādī killed the Rānī and

1. *Ibid.*

2. *The Cambridge History of India* (Vol. III), p. 327.

3. *Annual Report* (ASI) 1935-36, p. 100.

other 700 women of the palace and then set them to fire. Thereafter Silhādī, Lakhman Singh and 100 other Rajput relatives, clad in yellow robes, fell upon the Muslim forces who had escorted Silhādī to the fort under the guard of Alī Sher. Bahādur's army soon joined them and put them to sword.¹ Silhādī's one son and some followers, however, escaped and took shelter at Chittor.² Bahādur Shāh then took over the fort on the 10th May, 1532³ and appointed Sultān Ālam, the chief of Kālpī, as the governor of Raisen.⁴ The Gond king of Garhā-Manḍalā helped Bahādur Shāh in conquering the fort and earned the high-sounding title of "Sangrām Shāh."⁵

During the time of Bahādur Shāh at Mandu (1532) one Mallū Khān alias Kādir Shāh was granted Sārangpur and later appointed as the governor of Malwa.⁶

Originally, Bābar (1528), after entering Malwa, had a plan to conquer Raisen, Bhilsā and Sārangpur districts which were then held by Silhādī; but when he heard of the sad news of Humāyūn's defeat by Sher Shāh in the east, he gave up this plan.⁷

Humāyūn aimed at taking Gujarat from Bahādur Shāh. So he started from Agra and reached Raisen. The commandant of the fort gave him several presents and assured him that the fort belonged to him alone and the people in the fort were all his own followers. Humāyūn took a nominal possession of the fort and proceeded to Sārangpur. On this, Bahādur Shāh left Mandu for Gujarat and Silhādī's son Bhūpat Rāi, who was Bahādur Shāh's adviser, met Humāyūn with twenty soldiers.⁸

1. *The Cambridge History of India* (Vol. III), p. 328.

2. *The Delhi Sultanate*, p. 186.

3. *Bhopal State Gazetteer* (Vol. III), p. 113.

4. *The Cambridge History of India* (Vol. III), p. 328.

5. *Jabalpur Gazetteer* edited by P.N. Shrivastava, Bhopal, 1969, p. 76.

6. *Ibid.*, pp. 331-33.

7. *Rise and Fall of the Mughal Empire* by R.P. Tripathi, Allahabad, 2nd edition, 1960, pp. 46-47; *Bhopal State Gazetteer* (Vol. III), p. 77.

8. *The History of India as told by its own historians* by Elliot and Daweon (Vol. I), pp. 159-62; *Rise and Fall of the Mughal Empire*, pp. 76-77.

Humāyūn could not reach Mandu and shortly afterwards Mallū Khān became powerful with possession of Mandu, Ujjain, Sārangpur, Ranthambor etc. and in 1535 Bhūpat Rāi, who held Raisen, paid tribute to him.¹

Silhādī's son was Bhūpat Shāh and the latter's son was Partāb Shāh who also continued paying tribute to Mallū Khān. An inscription of the 19th August, 1542 in the Nizāmat gate of the Raisen fort refers to him as *Mahārājādhirāja* Pratāpasāhideva.² Partāb Shāh was a minor and Bhāi Pūran Mal, as his deputy, ruled holding the districts of Chanderī and Raisen.³ According to the same inscription in the Nizāmat gate he was known as *Mahārājakumāra* Pūrnamalladeva.⁴

After the death of Bahādur Shāh a confusion prevailed around Mandu and the adjoining territories. Pūran Mal immediately availed the opportunity and claimed independence.⁵ It is said that he was possibly an illegitimate son of Silhādī.⁶ His younger brother was Chhatar Mal⁷ or Chaturbhuj.⁸ According to the same Nizāmat gate inscription he is referred to as *Mahārājakumāra* Chandrabhānadeva.⁹ Pūran Mal's queen was Ratnāvalī. It is said that after occupying Chanderī, Pūran Mal massacred most of its inhabitants and collected 2000 ladies, both Muslims and Hindus, in his harem.¹⁰

1. *Bhopal State Gazetteer* (Vol. III), p. 113; *The History of India as told by its own historians* (Vol. IV), 1964, First Indian Edition, p. 391.
2. *Annual Report* (ASI) 1935-36, p. 100.
3. *The History of India as told by its own historians* (Vol. IV), p. 391.
4. *Annual Report* (ASI) 1935-36, p. 100.
5. *Rise and Fall of the Mughal Empire*, p. 122.
6. *Bhopal State Gazetteer* (Vol. III), p. 113.
7. *Ibid.*, p. 114.
8. *The History of India as told by its own historians* (Vol. IV), p. 392.
9. *Annual Report* (ASI) 1935-36, p. 100.
10. *The Cambridge History of India* (Vol. III), p. 370.

When Sher Shāh found that the Timurids (*i.e.* the Mughals) were advancing fastly to snatch away Malwa from him, he sent his son Kutb Khān to face them at Chondhā. He had also alerted the rulers of Raisen, Mandu, Ujjain etc. to assist Kutb Khān in his venture against the Timurids; but these principalities did not come to the rescue of Kutb Khān and he was in no time overpowered and slain by Mirzās Hindāl and Askarī, the Timurids. This calamity caused the greatest shock of his life to Sher Shāh and he developed a deep hatred and grudge against the whole kingdom of Mandu.¹ In 1542 Sher Shāh ousted Mallū Khān Kādir Shāh and appointed Shujaāt Khān as viceroy of Malwa. At Gagron Pūran Mal met Sher Shāh and paid homage to him.² On orders from Sher Shah, "Shujaāt Khān sent Rām-Shāh, the Tomar *Rājā* of Gwalior, to bring Pūran Mal of Raisen to the king. Pūran Mal wrote, saying that he would come if Shujaāt Khān himself went to fetch him. So Shujaāt went to the fort of Raisen and brought Pūran Mal with him to the king's presence. Upon his setting out, Ratnāvalī, the queen of *Rājā* Pūran Mal, sent words to Shujaāt Khān, saying—"I will then break my fast when I shall see Pūran Mal again; and the whole time he is away, I will sit on a bastion of the fort, and watch for his return." Shujaāt Khān requested her to be of good cheer, for that Bhaiā Pūran Mal would return to her next day. Shujaāt Khān brought Pūran Mal to the king's presence, with 6000 horsemen, none of whom were forty years of age. Sher Shāh instantly bestowed 100 horses and 100 splendid dresses of honour on Pūran Mal and allowed him to return. Bhaiā Pūran Mal left his younger brother Chaturbhuj to serve the king as a hostage."

But on the other hand, Sher Shāh used to say "Pūran Mal, who has enslaved the families of the Musalmans in Chanderī and has made dancing girls of their daughters, and did not accompany my son Kutb Khān—him I will so punish that he may be a warning to others, that hereafter no unbelievers in Hind may oppress and injure the families of Musalmans."

1. *The History of India as told by its own historians* (Vol. IV), p. 379.
2. *Ibid.*, p. 121.

“Jalāl Khān and Sher Shāh reached the vicinity of the fort of Raisen. Bhaiā Pūran Mal sent 600 elephants but did not himself come out. Sher Shāh thereupon laid siege to Raisen.”¹

“Sher Shāh gave orders that no Afghan should approach the fort for that he would take it by the exercise of his skill and prudence. One day, certain followers and retainers of the Afghans were sitting together when the conversation turned on the gallantry and valour of Bhaiā Pūran Mal’s soldiers. Most of those present said that no one in those days was a match for Pūran Mal’s soldiers in these qualities, who daily come out of the fort and said “There is no one in the army of Sher Khān who can fight with us and that it was for fear that none of the Afghans approached them.” When the Afghans, amongst these retainers pondered on these remarks, the reproach thus thrown upon Afghan honour overcame them. They said that “though Sher Shāh should cut our throats or banish us from his kingdom, yet we will for once encounter the soldiers of Pūran Mal.”²

“Next day, before sunrise, 1500 horsemen of Sher Shāh assembled at an appointed place, and in order of battle, went to Pūran Mal, saying—“Your men every day boast of their valour. We 1500 horse, against Sher Shāh’s command, have come and are drawn up in order of battle; do you also collect your men and come out of the fort, that we may fight and the valour of either side may be made manifest.” Bhaiā Pūran Mal had great reliance on the valour and gallantry of his men and did not think the Afghans were at all equal to them in bravery. He sent out to answer the challenge and most famous of his soldiers, veterans in battle, and he himself took his seat above the gateway. The Afghans and Rajputs joined battle, and the fight continued till the first watch of the day, upto which time neither party had succeeded in driving the other from their ground. At length, the Afghans got the advantage and began to make the Rajputs give ground. Such bravery was displayed on both sides as surpasses all description. In the end god gave victory to the Afghans and they drove the Rajputs from their position to near

1. *The History of India as told by its own historians* (Vol. IV), pp. 392-97.

2. *Ibid.*, (Vol. IV), pp. 399-400.

the gate of the fort. The Rajputs again made a stand near the gate but the Afghans made a headlong charge upon them, which they were unable to resist and fled within the gate and the Afghans returned triumphant to their camp. When Sher Shāh heard about it, he was pleased. He issued orders that the Afghans should bring all the brass in camp and make mortars (degħa) of it. With this mortar he ordered them to bombard the fort from all sides simultaneously. When they had battered the fort and breached it in all directions, Pūran Mal became alarmed, and after a lapse of six months he came out himself to Sher Shāh, who said to him—“I grant you quarter and government of Benares provided you give up the families of the Musalmans whom you have enslaved.” Pūran Mal replied—“I had none of these families, neither am I the *rājā*. I am but his deputy. I will go to him and I will say whatever you order me, and see what he replies.” Sher Khān permitted him to go. When he went up into the fort, he got together all his jewels and sent to Sher Khān saying—“I dare not again face your presence but do you first go away two marches from the fort. I will come out and give up the fort to your soldiers and go myself to other countries. And if your eldest son Ādil Khān and Kutb Khān Banet will bind themselves by promise and oaths that I shall suffer no injury in property or person, I will come with my women and family out of the fort.” Sher Shāh agreed. Kutb Khān Banet went upto the fort and binding himself by solemn oaths, brought Pūran Mal out of the fort of Raisen with his family and wives. Kutb Khān Banet requested that some encamping ground for Pūran Mal might be selected. Sher Shāh indicated a spot in the midst of his encampment and Kutb Khān Banet himself accompanied Pūran Mal to the spot Sher Shāh had directed.”¹

“After some days the widows of the chief men of Chanderī and others waited for Sher Shāh by the road-side and cried out to him—“We have suffered from this inhuman and malignant infidel all kinds of tyranny and oppression. He has slain our husbands, and our daughters he has enslaved and has made dancing-girls of them, and has seized lands, and all our worldly goods for a long time past. If you do not give us justice, hereafter, in the day of resurrection,

1. *The History of India as told by its own historians* (Vol. IV), pp. 400-01.

when the first and the last of all men shall be collected together, we will accuse you." Tears dropped from Sher Shāh's eyes. When consulted, two Ulamās including Amīr Shaikh Rafī'uddīn announced a decision for the death of Pūran Mal.

"At night orders were given to Īsā Khān Hajīb that he should desire his troops to collect with the elephants in all haste at a certain spot, for that Sher Shāh intended to make a forced march—towards Gondwānā. To Habīb Khān he gave secret orders that he should watch Bhaiā Pūran Mal and take care that he did not fly, and not to speak a word of this to any living creature, for that he (Sher Shāh) had long entertained this design. When the elephants and troops were at the appointed spot, they reported it to Sher Shāh, who ordered that at sunrise they should surround the tents of Bhaiā Pūran Mal. Pūran Mal was told that they were surrounding his encampment. Going into the tent of his beloved wife Ratnāvalī, who sang Hindi melodies very sweetly, he cut off her head; and coming out, said to his companions—"I have done this. Do you also slay your wives and families."¹

"While the Hindus were employed in putting their women and families to death, the Afghans on all sides commenced the slaughter of the Hindus. Pūran Mal and his companions fought gallantly like Rustam and Asfandyar but in the twinkling of an eye all were slain."²

One daughter of Pūran Mal and three sons of his elder brother were taken alive. Sher Khān gave the little daughter to some itinerant minstrels (*bāzīgārān*) that they might make her dance in the bazars and ordered the boys to be castrated, that the race of the oppressor might not increase."³

It is said that when Kutb Khān Banet saw the ghastly breach of faith by Sher Shāh with Pūran Mal, he felt such anguish that he committed suicide.⁴

1. *The History of India as told by its own historians* (Vol. IV), pp. 401-403.
2. *The History of India as told by its own historians* (Vol. VI), pp. 401-403.
3. *The History of India as told by its own historians* (Vol. IV), pp. 403 and 417.
4. *Rise and Fall of the Mughal Empire*, p. 124.

The ladies in the Rajput harem on the hill performed Jauhar.¹

Sher Shāh made over the fort to Munshī Shāhbāz Khān Acha-Khail Sarwānī and stationed a force together with 1000 artillerymen. He himself returned to Agra and remained at the capital during the rainy season. A Persian inscription on the western wall of the Dargāh of Pīr Fathullāh at Raisen records construction of a well during the time of Sher Shāh.

Later on, Islām Shāh, son of Sher Shāh, granted Sārangpur and country of Raisen to Shujaāt Khān in Jāgīr.² Till 1555 Shujaāt Khān held Malwa and Raisen. On his death, his son Miyān Bayāzīd or Bāj Bahādur succeeded him. He expelled his own younger brother Malik Mustafā from Raisen and retained it with him till 1561.³ Bāj Bahādur started a campaign against Durgāvātī, the queen of Goṇḍwānā between 1555 and 1560 but failed miserably.⁴ She faced Bāj Bahādur and the Miānā Afghans of Sironj several times and routed them with great success.⁵

During Akbar's time (1575) the Raisen fort was considered as one of the famous hill-forts of Hindustan, which in possession of the Solankī Rajputs, formed a Sarkār in the Sūbah of Ujjain.⁶

In 1584 the Raisen district was given in Jāgīr to Azam Khān (*i.e.* Mirzā Muhammad Kokā) who introduced Abul Fazl to Akbar.⁷

1. *The History of India as told by its own historians* (Vol. IV), pp. 403 and 417.
2. *Ibid.*, (Vol. IV), pp. 403-417.
3. *Ain-i-Ākbari* of Abul Fazl-i-Allami, (Vol. II), translated by H.S. Jarrett, 2nd edition, by Sir Jadunath Sarkar, Calcutta, 1949, p. 210.
4. *Jabalpur Gazetteer*, p. 77.
5. *Ibid.*, p. 78.
6. *Ain-i-Ākbari* of Abul Fazl-i-Allami, (Vol. II), translated by H.S. Jarrett, 2nd edition, by Sir Jadunath Sarkar, Calcutta, 1949, p. 210.
7. *Bhopal State Gazetteer*, (Vol. III), p. 77.

During the reign of Aurangzeb Ālamgīr (25th December 1691 and 25th March, 1695), the bastions and the ramparts (battlements) of the fort were repaired under the superintendence of Khwājā, the *Harīs* (Custodian), Sheikh Bahāuddīn Muhammad, the *Amīn*, Haji Muhammad, the *Musharraf*, Anūp Rāi, the *Tahvildār* during the governorship of Muhammad Mansūr, the governor and Muhammad Ābid Khān-i-Daurānī, the deputy (*Sazāwāl*), Gangā Rām being the mason (*Mīmār*) as per an inscription near the top-northern gate of the fort.¹

In 1751 the fort was in possession of Noid Alī Khān Khwājaserā, commandant for Ālamgīr II, who had become rebellious on account of the fall of the Timurids in Delhi. Nawāb Faiz Muhammad Khān (1742-77), son of Yār Muhammad Khān of Bhopal, snatched the fort from Noid Alī Khān. Ālamgīr II, however, welcomed him as commander of the fort.²

An Arabic and Persian inscription on one of the three guns kept near the Madāgan tank on the fort states that it was manufactured at the Rūm (Turkish) factory at Bhopal in the time (1763-64) of the same Faiz Muhammad Khān.³ It was during his time again (1773-74) that, as per a Persian inscription above the entrance of the Dargāh of Hazrat Fathullāh Shāh, its tomb was constructed during the governorship of Husain Khān, the Qiledār of Raisen, situated in the Sarkār of Ālamgīrpur Bhilsā in the Sūbā of Malwa,⁴ when Alī Gohar (*i.e.* Shāh Ālam II) ruled at Delhi. A Persian inscription on another gun refers that it was manufactured at the Rūm (Turkish) factory at Bhopal in the time of the minister Chhoṭe Khān Bahādur Shamsheer Jang of Bhopal, when Shāh Ālam II ruled at Delhi, on 12th February 1793.⁵

1. *The History of Bhopal*, p. 213.
2. *Ibid.*, p. 10.
3. *Epi. Ind.* (MO.) 1933-34, pp. 24-26, Pl. XIb (inscription No. 248). It speaks of Faiz Muhammad Khan as the son of Dost Muhammad Khan Bahadur Fath Jang.
4. *Ibid.*, (inscription No. 250).
5. *Epi. Ind.* (MO.), 1933-34, pp. 24-26, pp. XIb (inscription No. 249).

During the Nawābship of Hiyāt Muhammad Khān of Bhopal (1777-1808) his minister Morid Muhammad Khān surrendered the fort to Bālā Rao Angliā, governor of Sironj, who appointed Bhān Mul as its commandant. In 1797 Wazīr Muhammad Khān of Bhopal sent a force under Willāyat Muhammad Khān to oust Bhān Mul. The latter sent Kāsīm Khān, Gul Khān and Sultān Khān of Sironj to make terms with Willāyat Khān. Bhān Mul received Rs. 30,000 and threw the canons from the bastions into the moat, gun-powder into water and left the fort and went to Sironj. It is known as "*The Victory of Raisen by the Help of God.*" Then Nawāb Ghaus Muhammad Khān (1808-09) was appointed incharge of the fort. Thereafter, the fort remained with the rulers of Bhopal.¹

A Persian inscription above the small door of the dālān near the eastern gate of the same Dargāh, records the construction of the dālān and the gate of the mausoleum of Hazrat Fathullāh during the time of Nawāb Nazar Muhammad Khān of Bhopal (1817-18). It is worth noting that the present town of Raisen has a muhallā known as Nazarganj, mainly habited by the Muslims, having an old well and some Hindu Sculptures. This area is just at the foot of the fort at its northern side. There were a number of hutments and shops here and a road from here, through the Bhopāli gate, went to Bhopal, although now abandoned. A bazar was organised here every Thursday. In the Ward No. 2 of the present town of Raisen there is the "Hāthī-Darwāzā" through which the elephants used to go for drinking water in the Rām Tāl lake which was formed with the Ganeharā bandh, done in lime-mortar and stone. It is about one and half kilometers in length between the hill of the fort and the opposite hill of Sītātālāi. At the foot of the Sītātālāi hill, on this lake, there are a number of Muslim tombs including that of Pīr Jehāngīr.

The "Phūl Mahal" (*i.e.* the building now housing the Police Headquarters) was the residence of the Nawābs of Bhopal when on visit to Raisen. Generally, they maintained a brigade of about 700 soldiers at a time. The present-day Police-Station in Raisen is the same old Jail with its horse-barracks. And the present old collectorate

1. *History of Bhopal*, pp. 23, 24, 29, 210, 211 and 213.

represents the old Nizāmat, and its front road is one of the old roads of Raisen.

The recent Qiledārs of the fort were Thakur Umrāo Singh and Khudābux. The grandsons of the Thakur, S/Shri Yashwant Singh and Jang Bahādur Singh are still residing in Raisen. The last Qiledār was Muhammad Zaman Khān during the time of Sultān Jehān Begum in 1901.

It is said that the Qiledārs issued Chameli leaves bearing their permission for entry into the fort to the visitors. It was collected at the first gate of the fort.

The security force of the fort was gradually reduced from 2000 to 250 by Nawāb Sikandar Begam and then to 60 by Nawāb Shāh Jehān Begum.

At about mid-night the security men started on their vigil beating drums and flutes (*ramtūla*). This practice was known as "addhī" (i.e. mid-night watch). Hājī Mehtar was one of the flute-players.

In June, 1901 the fort was declared as a historical monument.

The fort has a massive and extensive wall with 9 gateways—4 to north including the Hāthī Darwāzā and 5 to South. There are 13 bastions—3 on east, 5 on north, 3 on west and 2 on south. The three Hindu palaces are known as Bādāl Mahal, Rājā Rohanī kā Mahal, Attardār kā Mahal. There are two mosques—College-mosque and Sher Shāh mosque. The fort has 4 tanks—Dūrā Dūrī, Madāgan, Sāgar and 48 wells.¹

The northern and the southern sides of the fort have massive stepped approaches with gateways. One of the northern gateways is called "Muḍiyā Darwāzā". In between this gateway and the top-gateway, a rock-bolder, shows an elephant with rider, who thrusts a spear in the mouth of a lion. Opposite to this scene, there is a horse-rider who attacks the same lion from its rear-side. The area covered by the scene is about 15' long and 8' wide. Of the five gateways on the south side, one is called the "Nizām or Nizāmat Darwāzā" and another one as the "gāḍī-Darwāzā."

1. Bhopal State Gazetteer, (Vol. III), p. 115.

Till 1870 Nawāb Shāh Jehān Begum counted 65 ruined constructions on the top. Out of them 45 were then intact. Some of them fell when struck by a lightning in 1875 and several lives were lost due to the fire in the magazine located on the top.

The royal palaces are two to three storeyes, generally quadrangular and provided with domes on their corners and sides and having underground cellars which were used during the summer seasons.

Outside the palace-area is a large 16th century A.D. temple which was converted as the Sher Shāh-mosque in 1543.

The college-mosque is just to the west of the royal palaces, known as Bārādārī now. There is a perennial spring of water here which now supplies water to the village people on the top of the fort and the visitors as well.

There are two Satī monuments with inscribed stone-slabs on the eastern end of the hill. One of the inscriptions refers to samvat 1766=A.D. 1709 and someone of the Khangāra race, probably a Rajput.

On the hill there are some large tanks :—

(1) To the west of the top-gateway, on the northern side of the fort, there was the Malanga like, now extinct.

(2) Below the twelve-pillared building and near the building housing presently the iron canon-balls is the Sāgar tank. The bastion near this tank accommodates the largest canon "*Garbhagirāvan*."

(3) Below the college-mosque is the Madāgan tank, which is the largest and ever full of water. Three bronze canons of the time of Nawāb Faiz Muhammad Khān of Bhopal (1742-77) lie to its south side.

(4) To the east of the college-mosque there is the Motiyātank built specially for use of the Royal family. It is about 100 ft. long and 80 ft. deep with steps inside.

(5) Rānī Tāl is another tank originally used by the ladies of the harem.

(6) The Dūrā-Dūrī tanks at the westren end below the Bālā fort are picturesquely situated. Strategically speaking, this is said to be the weakest point of the fort. A local tradition takes the words

“Durā-Durī” as Dolā-Dolī, thus referring to the occurrence that when Aurangzeb, the Mughal emperor of Delhi, laid siege to the fort of Raisen, his soldiers entered its gates in palanquins, dressed as ladies of his harem, who desired to meet the ladies of the Rajput harem. As soon as a large number of them got into the fort, they came out of the palanquins, drew their swords and fell upon the Rajputs. However, there is no record to substantiate the story. There is the grave of Svāmī Bhagat Bhāṭ, who, it is said, helped the enemies in getting forcibly into the fort on some critical moment.

The 48 tanks¹ are all cut here and there into the rocks to form cisterns. They made water available for use every where on the hill.

Around the fort also there were several tanks. Between the fort's hill and the Sītātalāi-hill there was the Ganeharā bandh, forming a large lake (Rām Tāl) in the north, now extinct. To the west of this bandh are the Ghoklā and Khajiyā tanks.

1. The local belief that there were “Chār Tāl Chaurāsī tanks” on the hill is, however, exaggerated.

MESOLITHIC SETTLEMENTS IN CENTRAL GUJARAT

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Mesolithic people flourished in Gujarat particularly in its Central region. The present paper presents a picture of the Mesolithic settlements in Central Gujarat which is based on excavations and explorations carried out at number of sites.

The geographical situation of the Indian sub-continent in general and Gujarat in particular is so favourable that it has attracted human settlements right from the earliest period of the history of the human beings. In Gujarat, particularly in Central Gujarat, Mesolithic men lived and flourished. This fact has been established through explorations and excavations. This paper deals with the excavation of a Mesolithic mound at Kanewal in Bhalbaru region of Kheda district in Central Gujarat which throws much light on this period of the Prehistory of Gujarat. The excavation revealed the ecological determinance and the fact that the hunting groups were in association with Post-Harappan Chalcolithic culture of Gujarat. The other excavation at Tarsang in Panchmahals proved to be a permanent settlement of Mesolithic man in Central Gujarat.

Central Gujarat comprises Kheda district and parts of its surrounding districts like Ahmedabad in the north-west, Panchmahals in the east, and Baroda and Bharoch in the south. On the south-west is the Gulf of Cambay (Plate 18).

Geographically the region could be divided into mountainous regions and plains. The north-eastern region of Central Gujarat has a large number of granite hills which slowly merge with the

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